

Networks of Displacement: Spatial and Temporal Dynamics of Post-WWII Migration and Resettlement

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The multi-phase process of spatial uprooting and violence-induced migration⁵⁹ caused by the Second World War is structurally characterized on a spatial and administrative level primarily by central locations⁶⁰ (hubs of displacement) where violence-induced migration is caused or negotiated. This uprooting posed major administrative challenges for states, NGOs, and, above all, international organizations such as UNRRA (United Nations Relief and Rehabilitation Administration) and later the IRO (International Refugee Organisation). While the majority of DPs (Displaced Persons) could be "repatriated" by the end of 1946, it was not possible for many DPs to simply return to their original place of origin.⁶¹ Their fates were "administered" by the IRO. Depending on demographic characteristics as well as spatial and temporal circumstances, this process varied for different subgroups.⁶²

Figure 1. Sketch of the Research Model.

This group was largely dependent on the IRO and other international actors for their spatial mobility and supplies. From a source-technical perspective, this makes it possible to draw on a rich stock of micro- and macro historical documents. The registration files of DPs that have applied to the IRO for "Care and Maintenance" (CM/1 files) form the basis of this. They not only allow DPs to be classified demographically based on the data collected but also their migration history from before displacement to resettlement to be

⁵⁹ There are usually different variations of pre-impact, impact and, post-impact phases.

⁶⁰ Such as Concentration camps, DP Camps, Forced Labour Camps, Nursing homes, Places of Transit, and Resettlement.

⁶¹ Ruth Balint, 2021: page 2.

⁶² Michael Marrus, 1987: page 345.

traced in spatial and temporal detail and linked to central "hubs of displacement".⁶³ Based on this source material, a sample of DPs who were successfully resettled via Austria to countries all around the globe is transferred to a relational database and modelled as a multilayer network in which the hubs are the nodes and the migration routes of the DPs are the connecting edges. The sample contains about 600 of 3600 sufficiently documented families (Arolsen Archives) who were picked by using a stratified sampling approach, based on available Mass-Data (Birthplaces, Age and Gender). Based on this model, an explorative, analytical approach is pursued with the help of network analysis, geo-information systems, and event modelling to reveal spatial, administrative and temporal patterns of the displacement process in its entirety and for demographic subgroups and, as a result, to make them accessible for subsequent qualitative research. The research model, from data collection to modelling to analysis, is shown schematically in Figure 1. The paper thus presents a multidimensional approach to analysing violence-induced and managed migration in a historical and institutional longitudinal section by using different digital-tools such as IGraph/NetworkX, ArcGIS/QGIS, GeoPandas/Pandas and OpenAtlas in a complementary analytical fashion.

The aim of the paper is therefore to present a methodological approach of combining network and spatial analysis and to discuss its potential for exploratory data analysis. Furthermore, the challenge of visualizing temporally dynamic processes in static network graphs and maps will be discussed.⁶⁴

References

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⁶³ Henning Borggräfe, Lukas Hennies, Christoph Rass, 2022.

⁶⁴ Cf. Rainer Schützeichel, 2012.